

2.3. EXPERIENCE OF EASTERN PARTNERSHIP COUNTRIES ASSOCIATED TO HORIZON EUROPE AND OTHER EU'S PROGRAMMES SUPPORTING EDUCATION, RESEARCH, INNOVATION, YOUTH AND SPORT

EaPConnect PROJECT - E-INFRASTRUCTURE AND SERVICES FOR RESEARCH AND EDUCATION SUPPORT

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ABSTRACT: Described the development trends of the national and regional e-infrastructures in Moldova and in Eastern Partnership (EaP) countries for effective support of research and educational activities. Considering important initiatives, approaches and solutions for development of modern e-Infrastructure resources for providing specific services to the research and educational communities in Moldova and other EaP countries. The transition of the traditional science and higher education to e-Science and e-Education is fueled by the ever increasing needs to have access, process and visualize of exceedingly large amounts of data that can't be managed without modern communication and computing instruments. e-Infrastructure designates a new generation of integrated ICT based resources, services and is widely considered as a key enabler for intensification of research and educational activities. Such infrastructures represent a distributed medium based on high-bandwidth networks, distributed computing resources, High Performance Computing (HPC) and respective data repositories. Special attention is focused on description of implementation of new Cross Border Fibers (CBF) connections in the region, other components of the e-infrastructures in the framework of the UE EaPConnect project. Created networking infrastructure is the basis for deployment and operation of national and regional e-Infrastructures that are providing wide range of specific services for universities and research centers. Argued importance of developing of Research and Educational networks as a key e-Infrastructures' enables. Described outcomes of regional and national projects in the area of e-infrastructures and modern services deployment for research and education.

Keywords: e-infrastructures, services for research and education, regional cooperation

Introduction. The e-infrastructure for science and education in the Republic of Moldova is based on the networking infrastructure of RENAM Association, which provides the necessary specific services, ensures interaction with the pan-European academic network GEANT and other European e-Infrastructures. Organizational structure of RENAM Association uses the European model attributed to a National Research and Education Network (NREN) aimed to support collaborative research of regional and pan-European scale that is realizing in a form of various international projects. Current trends in the modernization of e-infrastructures indicate the need to expand the capabilities of the main national e-Infrastructure components like external networking connections, the internal optical networking infrastructure of NREN, distributed and HPC computing resources in order to improve connectivity, offer possibility to elaborate complex applications and deploy modern services for support research and education.

Expanding the capabilities of national optical infrastructure and Cross Border Fiber (CBF) connections are the main directions of RENAM networking infrastructure development that is supported by international projects. In this direction it is important participation of RENAM in the European Commission (EC) initiatives focused on analyzing current state and activities of NRENs

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in the Eastern Partnership countries (Azerbaijan, Armenia, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine), developing appropriate proposals for the regional NRENs operation enhancement, implementation of effective connections to GEANT network.

It should be mentioned that during last few years important development of e-Infrastructures in EaP countries has been made, however there is still a visible gap between the developed European countries and the EaP region in access to modern services and resources of European and national e-Infrastructures. Support from National Governments and EU for the further development of e-Infrastructures in the region is essential for the integration of scientific potential of these countries in the European Research Area. Since 2015 EaP countries are participating in the regional initiative named EaPConnect that is supported by European Commission in a form of co-funded project. The project is intending to intensify take-up of specialized services, use of resources of existing and also developing e-Infrastructures to support research and educational activities in the region.

EaPConnect project activities can be structured in following directions:

- development of regional networking infrastructure and its interconnection with the pan-European GÉANT network;
- development of the national networking backbone infrastructure;
- deployment of the national computing facilities integrated into European level computing infrastructure;
- deploying and development of specific services focused on support of research and educational activities.

The number of users of various networking services, computing resources and data repositories in EaP countries is constantly growing. Key research applications and services that are developing in the region covering a wide range of scientific disciplines, such as earth and climate sciences, particle physics, life sciences, computational chemistry, economical behavior, mathematical modelling, computational engineering, etc. Accumulated experience of new networking and computing technologies application shows that for more active and effective use of available e-Infrastructure resources and services is necessary to reorganize users' support activities, activate new approaches of users' communities engagement, enhance educational and training activities, provide operative consultations for professionals to raise their skills in deployment and use of new demanded services.

1. Development of regional networking infrastructure for connecting EaP NRENs to GEANT. In Europe research and education networking infrastructure represented by GÉANT network that is interconnecting almost all European national research and education networks. GÉANT network operation and development is supporting by a serious of EU funded projects that endorse collaboration between 40 partners represented by European NRENs, including from EaP countries - Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine. GÉANT provides a high-bandwidth, first-class network infrastructure and services, connecting over 50 million users at over 10000 institutions across Europe.

Dialogue of NRENs from EaP countries with GEANT Association having the aim to investigate possible solutions for integrating EaP region to GÉANT and launch new initiative to support realization of proposed solutions was initiated in 2012. During EaPConnect project elaboration were analyzed requirements of national R&E users' communities in connectivity, computational resources and various specific IT services (Bogatencov, Astsatryan, Dombrougov et al, 2013). The accumulated information was used for EaPConnect project Concept Notes document elaboration, where systemized and analyzed information about needs in connectivity, resources of computing infrastructure, networking and other specific services for each EaP Country.

The development of the regional optical networking infrastructure for efficient access to the GEANT network and associated services required the identification of sustainable and cost-

effective technical solutions for new connections implementation. For this, a number of technical workshops were organized, in which specialists from GEANT, EU and EaP NRENs took part. The results of these studies and discussions allowed to form a common vision regarding the development of the regional network infrastructure in the Eastern Partnership region and recommendations for the use of long-term allocated DF or spectrum on fiber connections. The proposed regional network topology is consisting of two sub-regions that will have their own primary and back-up connections to GEANT:

- Eastern Europe networking segment, which covers NREN Belarus, Moldova and Ukraine;
- Caucasus Networking segment, which includes NRENs from three Caucasus countries.

The developed topology for Eastern Europe networking segment became the subject of implementation within the framework of the first stage of the EaPConnect project, during 2019-2021. At this stage a detail technical solution was developed to create a CBF connection between Moldova (NREN RENAM) and Ukraine (NREN URAN), to establish effective connections to GÉANT network PoPs in Poznan (Poland) and Bucharest (Romania) as development of regional communication arch implemented by support of the EaPConnect project that is now integrated in the GEANT optical networking backbone (Bogatencov, Secieru, Gaugas, Degteariov, 2021).

The general scheme of the implemented regional connectivity that is taking into account the requirements of RENAM and URAN, is shown in Figure 1. The realized solution based on results of previous studies and analysis of new RENAM and URAN connectivity requirements, overview of the available options to use DF, lambda or spectrum resources.

Fig. 1. RO-MD-UA-PL communication semi-ring based on CBF connections

To comply with general approach of GEANT backbone extension, for connecting of Eastern Europe NRENs to GÉANT network deployed new GEANT PoPs in Kiev and Chisinau. The initially elaborated technical proposal takes into account the long-term perspective of possible updates of the NRENs interconnection topologies and later it was extended by inclusion expansion of the GÉANT network in the Black Sea region for realization of new high-capacity and sustainable connections for South Caucasian countries.

2. Development of the national networking backbone in Moldova.

Implementation of new external connections to GEANT and analysis of RENAM users' needs obviously show necessity to extend capacity of internal optical infrastructure on the territory of Moldova. The development of the national backbone considering to be implemented in stage-by-stage manner.

3. Computing and Data Infrastructures for use by research and educational communities.

Recent two decades EU via different projects contributed to the building of the next generation pan-European and regional computing infrastructures for providing intensive computation and analysis of shared large-scale datasets. SEE-GRID (South East European Grid) regional initiative pushed to deploy sustainable national Grid infrastructures in the EaP countries and to integrate them into the pan-European and worldwide e-Infrastructures. Armenian, Georgian and Moldavian infrastructures were part of the SEE-GRID initiative. In parallel National Computing Grid Initiatives (NGI) have been established in EaP countries, which manage the computing resources provided to the national users’ communities and integrated into the European and regional computing infrastructures. In addition, NGIs are focusing on forming of national users’ communities, organization end user support, analyzing the needs of users, deploying demanded services for users’ communities.

In 2010 the European Grid Foundation (EGI) was launched. The goal of EGI-InSPIRE project (EU FP7 EGI-InSPIRE project, 2014) is to establish a sustainable European computing infrastructure and provide European scientists and their international partners with a sustainable, reliable distributed computing resources that can support their needs for large-scale data analysis and simulations. 51 national and international institutions from Europe and Asia Pacific region were partners of the project, among them organizations from Armenia, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine. Information about computing facilities in EaP countries is presented in Table 1.

Work on the implementation of National cloud infrastructure in Moldova began in 2013-2014, as a result of the participation of RENAM and the Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science (IMCS) in the regional project Experimental Deployment of an Integrated Grid and Cloud Enabled Environment in BSEC Countries on the Base of gEclipse (BSEC gEclipseGrid) supported by Black Sea Economic Cooperation Programme (Astsatryan, Hayrapetyan, Narsesian et al, 2013).

Table 1

Grid and cloud computing facilities in EaP countries

	Total Number of Sites	Number of Sites in EGI	Physical CPU EGI	Logical CPU EGI	Storage Capacity EGI, TB	Supported VOs
Armenia	8	2	148	592	27	6
Azerbaijan	3	0	84	336	72	4
Belarus	6	1	64	228	28	2
Georgia	2	1	74	300	28	5
Moldova	3	2	48	192	11	5
Ukraine	41	10	938	2372	455	45

Source: GRID statistics (2015)

The experience accumulated within this project resulted in installation of the Cloud infrastructure based on OpenStack version 13 Mitaka (release 2016), accessible at <https://cloud.renam.md/> and available for technology evaluation and applications testing. It was deployed using part of resources of two multiprocessor clusters of IMCS and RENAM. Despite the modest resources deployed, this infrastructure was widely used, both for evaluation purposes, and in several short-term projects and tasks in which it was necessary to deploy quickly a virtual infrastructure to test various scenarios, applications and products.

In 2018, the infrastructure was upgraded with modern high-performance servers. This upgrade has opened a new stage in the development of scientific Cloud computing facility – new resources were allocated for several projects in the field of Machine Learning and Neural Language

Processing. Since 2019 the created Cloud infrastructure began to use for new services – support of on-line lectures organization for the State University and the Technical University of Moldova. Although the deployed system had some disadvantages due to the limited number of available resources and lack of a high throughput network interconnection between nodes and storage elements, the experience gained over the years and user feedback made it clear the necessity of further development of National Cloud infrastructure (Degteariov et al, 2020).

To overcome the known limitations of the first realization of Cloud infrastructure in Moldova the State University of Moldova (SUM), IMCS and RENAM united efforts for developing and providing resources of the innovative federated Cloud environment that ensures the efficient use of available hardware and software resources for development of digital technologies for research and education (R&E) and solving problems that require high-performance computing resources and processing of large amounts of data. Computing facilities operated in SUM, RENAM and IMCS were upgraded: new high-performance servers for compute nodes and storage elements were installed; 10 Gbps optical network deployed between the main computing locations; IMCS and RENAM servers' rooms were modernized – modern uninterruptible power supply systems for server equipment and industrial air-cooling systems were installed. Current activities focused on deployment and development of HPC cloud infrastructure by implementing SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS service models for the joint use of parallel computing clusters integrated into a single distributed Cloud environment.

At the next stage of the distributed computing infrastructure development, it is planned to create a multi-zone IaaS Cloud infrastructure that combines existing and new perspective computing resources into one distributed computing network for processing scientific data, storing and archiving permanently increasing volumes of research data (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Multi-zone cloud: RENAM - IMCS – SUM

Distributed computing infrastructure will use the adaptive execution framework that can be adapted for the solution of different complex applications, certified and on-boarded as generic service to EOSC. The research team from SUM developed several applications that require resources of multiprocessor clusters integrated in the distributed Cloud infrastructure.

4. Services for regional and national research and educational communities

During the EaPConnect project proposal elaboration the analysis of the most demanded e-Infrastructure services in EaP region was produced (Bogatencov, Astsatryan, Dombrougov et al, 2014). The services developing in EaP countries enable to support the needs of researchers, students, educators and other user communities both at national and regional levels. The services proposed for implementation are grouped as presented in Figure 4.

EaPConnect project contributed to the deployment of the following groups of services in EaP countries:

1. Connectivity & network management: *eduroam* - wi-fi roaming; *perfSONAR* - PERFORMANCE Service Oriented Network Monitoring Architecture; *Software Defined Networks* - allow users themselves to manage parameters of the owned network infrastructure.

2. Trust & Identity: *Web Single Sign-On* - the federated service available to connect campuses via identity federations; *eduGAIN* - service for organization of inter-federation environments.

3. Specific/thematic: *Open Access initiative* - a value-added service for NRENs that is dedicated to support and promote open access to electronic publications; *Platforms and tools* for support of Open Science; *Real-time musical collaboration LOLA* (LOW LATency audio visual streaming system); *Digitization of Cultural Heritage*.

Fig. 4. Grouping of the implemented e-infrastructure services

In 2021 RENAM with methodological support of EaPConnect project and organizational assistance of the Ministry of Education and research of Moldova organized Users' Needs Assessment Survey to determine real needs national users' community in e-Infrastructure services offering by RENAM. Analysis of 170 responses received identified the following priorities of services take-up in Moldova:

- Need to increase external and internal connectivity (53% of responders);
- eduroam - wi-fi roaming (70% of responders);
- eduGAIN and identity management services (72% of responders);
- Video conferencing (70% of responders);
- Research data virtual archiving service (61% of responders);
- Virtual learning environment service, such as Moodle, integrated with real-time communications (60% of responders);
- Use of the Cloud computing resources (52% of responders).

Conclusion

During the last few years important development of e-Infrastructure in EaP countries has been made. The realization of regional projects like EaPConnect significantly contribute to development

of the high-quality networking infrastructure, well-developed informational services deployment and also to providing access to European Research Infrastructures with global impact for research and educational communities in EaP region.

Complementary support from National Governments and EC of the further development of e-Infrastructure and associated services in the region is essential for the take-up modern educational technologies, integration of scientific potential of EaP countries in the European Research Area.

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